

Non-Critical Medical Devices such as Clinical Thermometers and Sphygmomanometer (Blood Pressure) Cuffs are Potential Vectors for Hospital-Acquired Infections: A Case Study of a Tertiary Care Hospital in North-Central Nigeria

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Abstract

*Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) also known as nosocomial infections have been a persistent public health challenge particularly in developing countries. HAIs are also referred to as healthcare-associated infections. Often times, greater priority has been given to invasive diagnostic or therapeutic medical and surgical devices while the non-critical medical devices have been neglected by healthcare providers. This study aimed at evaluating the ability of non-critical medical devices such as clinical thermometers and sphygmomanometers (blood pressure cuffs) in HAI transmission at Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BhUTH), Jos, Plateau State, North-Central Nigeria. A total of 27 swabs from clinical thermometers and blood pressure (BP) cuffs were obtained from various hospital units and analyzed in the microbiology laboratory of the same hospital using standard microbiological techniques. Obtained results revealed bacterial contaminations of clinical thermometers and BP cuffs at 66.7% and 86.7% respectively. Alarming, 92.3% and 88.9% of the hospital units showed contamination of clinical thermometers and BP cuffs respectively. The major isolated bacteria were *Staphylococcus aureus* (84.2%), *Escherichia coli* (21.0%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (5.2%). *S. aureus* and *E. coli* isolates were resistant to all the beta-lactam antibiotics such as amoxicillin and cefuroxime. However, all the isolates were susceptible to ciprofloxacin and streptomycin. Non-critical medical devices harbor pathogenic bacteria and can be transmitted to patients and healthcare workers. Therefore, there is an urgent need for quality control and contamination surveillance on non-critical medical devices. Frequent sanitization (in between patients), washing or replacement (at intervals) of the clinical thermometers and BP cuffs is also highly recommended.*

Keywords: Antibiotics resistance, Bacterial infections, Blood pressure cuffs, Case study, Clinical thermometers, Healthcare-associated infections, Hospital-acquired infections, Non-critical medical devices, North-central Nigeria, Nosocomial infections, Sphygmomanometers, Tertiary care hospital, Vectors..

Received: 07.02.2026

Revised: 16.02.2026

Accepted: 23.02.2026

Published: 26.02.2026

Funding: This research did not receive any financial support.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

How to cite: Iorhemba TM, Ikwuka AO, Adeniran TA, Irogho JO, Ichivir OE, Silas LP. Non-Critical Medical Devices such as Clinical Thermometers and Sphygmomanometer (Blood Pressure) Cuffs are Potential Vectors for Hospital-Acquired Infections: A Case Study of a Tertiary Care Hospital in North-Central Nigeria. *J Clin Pract Med Res*, 2026;2(2):5-11. DOI: 10.59324/jcpmr.2026.2(2).02

Introduction

Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), also known as nosocomial infections, are a major but often underrated public health challenge worldwide. HAIs are among the major complication of modern medical treatment. HAIs include infections acquired in the hospital but appearing after discharge, and occupational infections among staff of a healthcare facility. The cited case-fatality rate ranges from 2.3% to 14.4% depending on the type of infection [1].

According to the World Health Organization, HAI could be acquired as an infection in a hospital or other healthcare facilities by a patient in whom the infection was not present or incubating at the time of admission [2, 72]. Reports indicate that at any time, more than 1.4 million people worldwide are estimated to suffer from infections acquired in hospitals [2, 3, 72]. It was noted that because of an increase in invasive procedures and a growing resistance to antibiotics, HAIs have increased by 36.0% in the last 20 years and are consuming more healthcare resources each year [4, 72]. The burden these infection places on healthcare systems can be categorized into three viz the cost of quality, the cost in human lives, and the financial impact [4].

Likewise, Metabolic Syndrome Diseases (MSDs) such as hypertension, adiposity (obesity), diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia are interrelated diseases which have very high morbidity and mortality rates [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. Moreover, it has been reported in different studies that hypertension, adiposity (obesity), diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, asymptomatic hyperuricemia [11-13], systemic immune inflammation activation, and fibrogenesis can lead to kidney damage [14-23, 73].

Nonetheless, in most developing countries, particularly in resource-poor settings, the estimated rate of HAI ranges from 25.0% to 40.0% and this exerts a tremendous toll on patients, families, communities, and healthcare systems, resulting in a significantly increased morbidity and mortality, and increasing the cost of health [24, 25, 72].

Over the years, high-risk invasive diagnostic and therapeutic healthcare tools have been prioritized in the prevention of HAI, while less attention has been given to non-critical tools [4, 26]. Recent studies have reported the potential nosocomial spread of microbial flora by means of non-critical healthcare tools including scissors [27], stethoscopes [28, 29], tourniquets [30], ultrasound transducers [31], gloves [32], pens of physicians and nurses [33], white coats [26, 34], thermometers [35], and blood pressure (BP) cuffs [26, 36, 37].

In addition, thermometers and BP (sphygmomanometer) cuffs are among the most commonly used non-critical medical devices (NCMDs) in hospital settings. Both have been associated with the spread of HAI in healthcare facilities [36, 37, 72]. Thermometers have been linked with the outbreaks of nosocomial infections in critical hospital units such as the intensive care unit (ICU), neonatal, and burns units [35, 38]. An older research found that the electronic thermometer was the vehicle that caused the outbreak of vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecium* in a medical/surgical intensive care unit, and ward of a university hospital [39, 72].

Similarly, a number of investigations including very recent studies have identified BP cuffs as the potential vehicle for transmission of nosocomial infection in selected patient populations [36, 37, 40, 72]. Most studies recorded NCMDs contamination rates ranging from 25.0% to 100%. BP cuffs have been associated with outbreaks of mupirocin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) with a range of 2.3% to 32.0%, and borderline methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus* (BMSSA) in various hospitals [1, 41- 43, 72].

In the face of increasing awareness of the roles of NCMDs in HAIs, there is limited information on the contributory role of these devices to the

burden of HAI in developing nations [72]. A literature review showed that most studies on NCMDs and transmission of HAIs originated from western countries. Therefore, the aim of this present study was to assess the potential contribution of thermometers and BP cuffs to HAIs in a Nigerian teaching hospital. Thus, the objectives of this present study were to evaluate the microbial contamination profile of clinical thermometers and BP cuffs used by healthcare workers, to determine the antibiotics susceptibility pattern of these microbial isolates to commonly used antibiotics, and to discuss the general implications of the study findings, control, and prevention of HAIs.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The microbial samples were collected between February and April 2023 at Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BhUTH), Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Sampling Technique

Clinical thermometers and sphygmomanometer (BP) cuffs used in the various units of the hospital were sampled. These units include accident and emergency, emergency pediatrics, general outpatients, intensive care, managed care, maternity, medical outpatients, medical ward, operation theater, pediatric ward, physiotherapy, private ward, and surgical ward. Briefly and using sterile gloves, an estimated skin-touching surface area of 100cm² of the clinical thermometers and BP cuff materials were swabbed using a sterile swab stick dipped in physiological saline. Swab sticks were recapped immediately, labeled appropriately, and transported to the microbiology laboratory of the same hospital.

Laboratory Methods

The swabs were gently inoculated directly on different freshly prepared blood agar, MacConkey agar, and nutrient agar plates. The inoculated media were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 hours and then examined for bacterial growth according to standard procedure [44, 72]. Cultural characteristics were analyzed, thereafter Gram reaction was performed. Biochemical tests such as catalase and coagulase, triple sugar iron agar test, hemolysis and sugar fermentation, oxidase tests, citrate utilization, and urease activity were done using procedures described by [45]. More than three colony forming units (>3CFUs) were considered before speciation as a contaminant [28]. Bacterial isolates were subjected to antibiotics sensitivity testing using Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method [44, 46]. The antibiotics disk and its potency used in this present study include Amoxicillin (30µg), Ampiclox (30µg), Ceftriaxone (25µg), Cefuroxime (20µg), Ciprofloxacin (10µg), Cotrimoxazole (30µg), Erythromycin (10µg), Gentamicin (10µg), Pefloxacin (10µg), and Streptomycin (30µg). The antibiotics disk is a product of Maxicare Medical Laboratory Limited (Nigeria).

Data Analysis

Statistical analyses including mean, median, mode, and percentages were calculated using Microsoft Excel and SPSS version 26.

Ethical Considerations

The approval for this study was conveyed via a letter with Ref. No. NHREC/21/05/2005/00885 from the Health Research and Ethical Committee of Bingham University Teaching Hospital (BhUTH), Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Results

Table 1 shows that 8 (66.7%) out of 12 clinical thermometers sampled had bacteria contaminations.

Table 1: Bacterial contamination profile of clinical thermometers

Hospital Unit	No. of clinical thermometers sampled	No. of clinical thermometers contaminated	Percentage of clinical thermometers contaminated
Accident & Emergency	1	1	100.0
Emergency Pediatrics	2	1	50.0
General Outpatients	-	-	-
Intensive Care	1	1	100.0
Managed Care	-	-	-
Maternity	1	1	100.0
Medical Outpatients	-	-	-
Medical Ward	2	2	100.0
Operation Theater	2	-	0.0
Pediatric Ward	1	0	0.0
Physiotherapy	1	1	100.0
Private Ward	1	1	100.0
Surgical Ward	-	-	-
Total	12	8	66.7

Table 2 shows that out of the 15 blood pressure cuffs sampled, 13 (86.7%) were contaminated by bacteria.

Table 2: Bacterial contamination profile of sphygmomanometer (blood pressure) cuffs

Hospital Unit	No. of BP cuffs sampled	No. of BP cuffs contaminated	Percentage of BP cuffs contaminated
Accident & Emergency	1	1	100.0
Emergency Pediatrics	1	1	100.0
General Outpatients	1	1	100.0
Intensive Care	1	1	100.0
Managed Care	1	1	100.0
Maternity	1	1	100.0
Medical Outpatients	1	1	100.0
Medical Ward	2	2	100.0
Operation Theater	2	1	50.0
Pediatric Ward	1	0	0.0
Physiotherapy	1	1	100.0
Private Ward	1	1	100.0
Surgical Ward	1	1	100.0
Total	15	13	86.7

Table 3 shows an array of bacterial species isolated from clinical thermometers and BP cuffs.

Table 3: Bacterial isolates from clinical thermometers and BP cuffs

Bacterial isolates	Clinical thermometers (n=12)		BP cuffs (n=15)		Overall total (n=27)
	No. of isolates	% of isolates	No. of isolates	% of isolates	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	6	75.0	10	76.9	16 (84.2)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	2	25.0	2	15.4	4 (21.0)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	-	1	7.7	1 (5.2)
Total	8	66.7	13	86.7	21 (77.8)

Among the bacterial isolates, *Staphylococcus aureus* shows 75.0% and 76.9% for clinical thermometers and blood pressure cuffs respectively, followed by *Escherichia coli* with 25.0% and 15.4% for clinical thermometers and blood pressure cuffs respectively, while

Pseudomonas aeruginosa was not isolated from clinical thermometers and had 7.7% for blood pressure cuffs (see Table 3).

The antibiotic resistance profiles of these bacterial isolates are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Antibiotics resistance profiles of the bacterial isolates from clinical thermometers and blood pressure cuffs

Antibiotics	Concentration	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
Amoxicillin	30µg	100.0	75.0	0.0
Ampiclox	30µg	87.5	25.0	0.0
Ceftriaxone	25µg	75.0	0.0	0.0
Cefuroxime	20µg	100.0	50.0	0.0

Ciprofloxacin	10µg	25.0	0.0	0.0
Co-trimoxazole	30µg	43.8	0.0	0.0
Erythromycin	10µg	31.2	0.0	0.0
Gentamicin	10µg	50.0	0.0	0.0
Pefloxacin	10µg	62.5	25.0	0.0
Streptomycin	30µg	25.0	0.0	0.0

Discussion

Only a few studies have been done on the relevance of non-critical medical devices in the transmission of HAIs in healthcare settings particularly in developing nations. Despite laid out guidelines on basic de-germ and decontamination of non-critical medical devices by hospitals, these guidelines have been largely neglected by healthcare providers.

On the other hand, the high economic cost, high morbidity rates, and high mortality rates associated with metabolic syndrome diseases (MSDs) have been mentioned. MSDs can cause kidney damage. Kidney damage can lead to anemia due to decreased secretion of erythropoietin [47, 48, 49, 50]. It has been reported that stress can compromise immunity [51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56]. Linked with the induction of oxidative stress are major free radicals. Among these major free radicals, superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical, and hydroperoxyl radical are of physiological significance. Non-radical of physiological significance is hydrogen peroxide [57, 58, 59, 71, 74]. Increased oxidative stress can induce alteration in the DNA sequence of an organism thereby causing mutation [60].

The results obtained from this present study revealed that clinical thermometers and blood pressure cuffs conceal bacteria contaminations with most of these bacteria being multi-drug resistant, thereby posing not just a threat in the transmission of infections, but more difficulties in treating these infections.

The clinical thermometers sampled in this present study had 66.7% of bacterial contamination. This high contamination rate is indeed worrisome. A previous study carried out at a medical center in Amsterdam, The Netherlands observed a nosocomial outbreak of multi-resistant *Enterobacter cloacae* in the neonatal ICU due to contaminated thermometers [35].

The bacteria contamination of blood pressure cuffs (86.7%) observed in this present study is also worrisome and alarming. Blood pressure apparatus is one of the most commonly used medical device. However, due to the hurried nature of operating theaters, emergency departments, intensive care units (ICUs), contaminated blood pressure cuffs may not be routinely sanitized or replaced with clean cuffs in between patients [40, 75].

The high bacterial contamination observed on the blood pressure cuff in theaters where reasonable level of sterility is expected may compromise the success rate of the surgeries been performed leading to increased hospital stay as well as increased use of post-surgical antibiotic prophylaxis and ultimately increased morbidity and mortality. Bacteria have been observed to survive for up to five days on blood pressure cuffs and there is a need for awareness of the potential cross-contamination to patients and healthcare workers from seemingly innocuous items of generally used hospital equipment particularly BP cuffs [61, 72].

Interestingly, all the sampled clinical thermometers and BP cuffs from the medical ward showed 100% bacterial contamination which indicates a high chance of infection acquisition and transmission. However, these same devices from the pediatric ward showed no bacterial contamination. The low number of clinical thermometers sampled was due to the fact that some of the hospital units such as the general outpatients, managed care, medical outpatients, and surgical ward had

only infrared thermometers. Thus, they did not meet the inclusion criteria.

Findings from antibiotic susceptibility test presented in Table 4 showed that all *S. aureus* isolates were resistant to beta-lactam group of antibiotics such as amoxicillin (100.0%), ampiclox (87.5%), ceftriaxone (75.0%), and cefuroxime (100.0%). This finding is indeed of public health relevance because these resistant isolates can spread into communities and infections resulting from them might be difficult to treat. This finding from this present study corroborates the finding from a previous study [26] where isolated *S. aureus* from non-critical medical devices were found to be resistant to flucloxacillin, ampicillin-cloxacillin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, and ampicillin. This development raises high suspicions of the presence of methicillin-resistant *staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA).

In addition, this present study revealed that *S. aureus* had the highest resistance profile and also had its highest susceptibility to streptomycin (75.0%), but the isolates were all 100% resistant to amoxicillin and cefuroxime. However, the *E. coli* isolates showed 100% susceptibility to ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, co-trimoxazole, erythromycin, gentamicin, and streptomycin. Nevertheless, *P. aeruginosa* showed 100% susceptibility to all the antibiotics tested.

Moreover, the presence of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase resistance genes associated with *Salmonella typhi* isolated from this same health facility used in this present study was reported in 2024 by [50]. Antibiotic resistance has proven to be of great public health concern as it has led to an increase in the cost of treatment, reduced productivity, prolonged hospital stay, urgent need to manufacture newer antibiotics, and ultimately to increased morbidity and mortality rates. The irrational use of antibiotics, as well as other socio-economic factors such as poverty, illiteracy, etc have contributed largely to antibiotic resistance. It is also interesting to note that results from different studies have pointed out how treatment in patients with Metabolic Syndrome Diseases (MSDs) can be optimized. For instance, Sodium-Glucose Linked Transporter 2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors e.g. Dapagliflozin [62-69, 76], and Glucagon-like Peptide 1 Receptor Agonists (GLP-1 RAs) e.g. Liraglutide [70] have been found to improve the efficacy of treatment and clinical course [74] of disease in MSD patients with co-morbid pathologies of type 2 diabetes mellitus and hypertension.

It is therefore recommended that a more robust quality control and surveillance mechanism on antibiotics resistance patterns of bacteria associated with non-critical medical devices within hospital settings be instituted in healthcare settings. Also recommended is the frequent washing or replacement of the BP cuffs at intervals, and sanitization of both the clinical thermometers and BP cuffs in between patients.

Conclusion

Non-critical medical devices (NCMDs) such as clinical thermometers and sphygmomanometer (blood pressure) cuffs are possible vectors for the transmission of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) in healthcare settings. Although, the chances of infection transmission from these non-critical medical devices are low, the chances are however higher in individuals who have direct contact with these devices on a regular basis.

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